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METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES IN ANALYZING CONSUMER RESPONSES TO ADVERTISING

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Abstract

This paper will focus on the main methodological issues for a comparative research of consumer responses in advertising. Ad-testing or copy testing is a general term often used by practitioners in advertising research for testing ads' effectiveness based on consumers' responses. To be able to effectively measure any kind of advertising impact we must focus on how advertising works. Thus after reviewing academic literature as well as practitioners' research suggestions, we first focus on terminology, research framework and the analysis of the context of the research. The article ends with a critical analysis where suggestions for further research are made.

Keywords: Advertising, gender, age, emotion, bias

Introduction

In modern times marketing is increasingly more dependable on advertising thus measuring advertising effectiveness is of great interest for many disciplines ranging from sociology, psychology to economy. There is abundance of different theories and as a consequence many volumes of different scales in numerous articles. Despite the quantity of articles with regard to measuring consumer responses to advertising there is little agreement on the suitable methodology. In addition, there is even less consensus when advertising contains elements of emotional persuasion. The emotional component in advertising is the reason that Hall (2004: 2) recently suggested a "complete rethinking of some new and a careful reconsideration of old tools for measuring the effects of advertising.

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The new tools should bring affective measures to the forefront, where modern psychology and neuroscience suggest.”

Even in 2021 we have to agree with Poels and Dewitte (2006: 19) that “... to date, advertising literature is not straightforward on what instrument provides the most valid emotion measurement” and a construct of how to measure advertising effectiveness has no “perfect” solution. We understand that we can therefore only optimize our design for a specific context. Already in 1967 Marshall McLuhan, a legend in advertising, stated that the medium itself influences the reception of a message and acts independently from content (1967: 209).

In this paper, we will focus not only on the relevant academic literature but also on practitioners’ experiences. This makes the research design compliant with the theory as well as useful for future research. We aim to discuss the question why consumers react as they do and not only if they react. By setting the focus on consumer research, we will divide consumers into different segments and analyze them separately. Thus, we can increase the practical value of the research.

Gender differences

Gender differences play an important role when deciding on an advertising strategy. Buck, Anderson, Chaudhuri, & Ray suggest (2004: 655) that women react differently to emotions stimulated in advertising. According to Baird, Wahlers and Cooper (2007: 50-52) it also seems that retention of emotional appeals is higher for women. Similarly Lombardot (2007: 31-34) sees the absence of symmetry between reactions from men and women. He argues that the “necessity to distinguish between respondents according to their gender is such that each hypothesis presented needed to be validated twice; once for men and once for women.” Finally, Moore claims (2007: 205) that too little research has been done in the context of the influence of gender on advertising effectiveness and therefore we find it essential to include gender as an independent variable.

Age groups

In his extensive preview of the literature relating the aging and consumer responses Greuoir (2003: 19-23) urges to extend research in this area. Researchers must recognize not only the growing size but also the economic importance of the older consumer segment. Williams, Patti, & Drolet, Aimee (2005: 344) point out a “decline in working memory capacity of older adults’ performance on many tasks resembles that of young adults under cognitive load” in order to focus on emotional versus information. They also suggest, “Specifically, older adults had higher liking and recall of emotional appeals” (2005: 351). Rousseau, Lamson and Rogers (1998: 657-662) thus provide evidence of age related declines in vision and audio abilities. The elderly perform less than younger people with regard to the following visual abilities: color, vision, contrast sensitivity, glare sensitivity, temporal resolution, visual accuracy and visual search. These age-related changes associated to these abilities might affect in many ways how older people will perceive a message and are therefore included in the research design. On the other hand, younger consumers from 18 to 29 differ from general consumers on the cognitive responses (for example sources of information), affective responses (for example attitude towards new technologies) and behavioral responses (for example purchase of products, purchase of brands and complaining). Williams, Patti, & Drolet, Aimee (2005: 344) argue in their research that young adults had higher liking and recall of rational appeals than older adults, implying that they might react differently to ads.

Other potential independent variables

Involvement and personal characteristics are usually not included in the model as independent variables for two reasons. The first is that we look at the consumer market from a social mass media and not from the personality-oriented point of view. In a consumer market, due to a number of consumers, a normal distribution of individual characteristics of consumers as well as purchase involvement situations is expected. The second reason is the fact that we are usually conducting a comparative research between two different media types and are, due to the complexity of the research, interested in relative not absolute measures as suggested by Braun and Zaltman (2006: 70). These dispositions and generalizations, however, allow us to extend the usefulness of the research design to other media comparisons as well as individual ad copy testing.

Attention and engagement

After reviewing more than 400 articles, we found out that the term attention is used very frequently and in very different meanings, contexts. Young (2010: 3), for example, equates attention with stopping power. Visual attention can thus be defined as in Ketelaar, Gisbergen, Bosman and Beentjes (2008: 16) as “the allocation or concentration of cognitive energy to process one part of the visual field at the expense of other parts.” Similarly, Cummings (2007: 6) defines attention as “a concentration of the mind on a single object or thought, especially one preferentially selected from a complex, with a view to limiting or clarifying receptivity by narrowing the range of stimuli.”

Heath (2007b: 7-8) further limits the term attention and argues that the level of attention consists of “conscious thinking going on when an advertisement is being processed.” In respect of the levels of attention and learning, Heath describes high attention (fully conscious thinking) as “active learning”, and low attention (semi-conscious thinking) as “passive learning”. Learning which takes place without any attention is subconscious and is termed “implicit learning.”

In cases where consumers have low or no attention but still experience the effects of advertising, a further term must be defined. Thus, a term engagement was a response that advertising and marketing professionals¹ made to emphasize the importance and relevance of the emotional connection to buyer behavior as delivered through advertising. The ARF (2007: 7) definition of engagement is “turning on a prospect to a brand idea enhanced by the surrounding context”. While no consensus exists, many researchers define engagement as “the amount of feeling going on when an ad is processed”. This definition reflects Heath’s (2007b: 8) definition of the level of engagement as the amount of subconscious “feeling” going on when an advertisement is being processed. Heath (2007b: 8) suggests that the amount of engagement (feeling which goes on when an advertisement is processed) is dictated by the amount of emotional content in the advertisement and thus high levels of emotional content will equate with high levels of engagement and

¹ Advertising Research Foundation (ARF), the American Association of Advertising Agencies (AAAA), and the Association of National Advertisers (ANA) have defined this concept as well as developed metrics to measure it.

thus engagement can be measured by the emotional content of advertisements.

It is important to understand that Heath's definitions of engagement and attention as above defined do not overlap and together describe a "sum" reaction of the consumer to advertising. Many authors assume that engagement and attention are causally connected to one another. However, Heath (2007b: 12) provided research evidence "that engagement and attention, as represented by emotional and rational content in advertising, operate independently and that there is no direct relationship between levels of attention and levels of engagement." It seems possible to be highly emotionally engaged in advertising and yet not be paying much attention, or to be highly emotionally engaged and paying a lot of attention. There is no consensus on definitions, however, it is clear that in order to be effective "print advertisement must get noticed and attract a reader" (Young, 2010: 3). According to Heath (2007b: 18), achieving "nor attention nor engagement means you are in serious danger of having unsuccessful ads."

As we acknowledge the importance of attracting attention and engagement, we focus on different suggestions about how to measure them. Researchers can use self-report techniques or different observations. One of the more promising self-report techniques, as suggested by Young (2001: 475), is asking the respondent, "Which of the ads you just saw did you find interesting?" The author warns that this is not a measure of memory or recall but simply a measure of audience interest. He argues that this measurement correlates very strongly with ads that have won major creative award shows and gives the measure validity. On the other hand, observation of the consumers can differ substantially. Ketelaar, Gisbergen, Bosman, & Beentjes (2008: 17-20) used a very popular (but expensive) equipment for eye-tracking to present evidence that viewing time refers to the duration of attention that is devoted to the ads; longer fixation durations indicate more processing and therefore deeper levels of attention.

With respect to the context of research, we suggest an alternative method for measuring the combined effect of attention and engagement in outdoor advertising. We argue that the only relevant measure of attention can be executed in a realistic environment. If advertisers want to achieve overall effective advertising they need to

achieve engagement or attention that can be seen in the existence of stopping power. We also find stopping power as a necessary but not self-sufficient measure of advertising effectiveness. It is only important when it leads to other positive effects, for example, a change of consumer attitude and purchase intention.

Categorization of ads - cognitive and emotional advertising components

Chandy, Tellis, Macinnis and Thaivanich (2001: 408) provide evidence that as consumer markets are getting “older”, consumers are already educated about the rational value of products and services. In these markets argument based ads are likely to become less effective. On the other hand, emotion-based ads become more effective as markets get older. The Cambridge Dictionary of Sociology (2006: 163-164) defines emotions as “experiences of involvement.” For the purpose of this paper, we narrow this definition as in Heath (2007: 3) to “any stimulation of the feelings, at any level that is capable of stimulating the feelings of the viewer.” Using this definition, emotional content does not have to produce an overt “emotional” response by the consumer and is compliant with The Cambridge Dictionary of Sociology where “emotions, including the most important for social processes, are experienced below the threshold of awareness.”

Closely connected to emotions is affect. The term affect “denotes the emotional or feeling element (as distinct from the purely cognitive element) of mental experience” (Sage Dictionary of Sociology, 2006: 5) and is according to Erevelles (1998: 199) usually defined as a “valenced feeling state.” Erevelles also defines mood and emotion as instances of this state where mood is relatively low in intensity and is usually not associated with a stimulus object. Emotion, on the other hand, is higher in intensity, and is usually associated with a stimulus object.

Sørensen (2008: 3) stresses that the importance of including emotional aspects in consumer research is “even greater than was earlier recognized.” In addition, Brader (2005: 388), when analyzing the extent to which campaign ads affect voting behavior by stimulating emotions, explains, “emotions play a fundamental role in reasoning and are as likely to enhance rationality as to subvert to it.” According to his experiments, emotional cues also affect the search for information relevant to the issues raised in an ad.

In reviewing the literature, Vakratsas and Ambler (1999: 36-37) argue that emotions play an even larger role in decision-making than assumed and suggest that affect can be even more important than cognition. The idea that rational decisions are the most important and that emotion and feelings are only noise has been rejected by Damasio (2004: 7-11) who explains that decision-making is not possible without the influence of emotions. Extensively cited author Heath (2006: 417) shows evidence that the “emotional creative content in advertising is the one that builds strong brand relationships, not the rational message.” His suggestion (2006: 418) is that if advertising wishes to build strong brand relationships, it needs to incorporate high levels of emotional content, and this emotional content will be most effective if less attention is paid to it. Similarly Young (2009: 43-45), a research director of a famous research company Ameritest, claims that the most effective ads are those that generate emotional and rational thoughts. On the point, whether to use emotional or rational advertisements he argues that “all effective commercials contain elements where both rational thinking and emotion comes together.” To sum up, in the context of advertising research “the need to” consider emotions and affect is vital. As in Young (2004b: 202) the issue is not “whether emotions in advertising matter, the problem is how to measure it.”

Selection and creation of stimuli (ad)

Geuens, Pelsmacker and Faseur (2010: 3) namely showed that emotional ads lead to a significantly more positive attitude towards the brand for high involvement products. Secondly, the same authors argue that emotional ads lead to a better ad and brand attitude for hedonic products but lead to a similar attitude towards the brand as non-emotional ads for utilitarian products. They suggest that an emotional appeal harms none of the products but that the same appeal works better for some products than others because the products themselves evoke different associations. Finally, as pointed out by Ketelaar, Gisbergen, Bosman and Beentjes (2008: 22), since the presence of headlines influences viewing times of consumers to print ads, a research must keep the size and location of headlines constant in all test situations.

Models on consumer responses to advertising

To be able to develop a research design that is compliant with the theory as well as with 21st century practitioners' experiences, we have to analyze and select an appropriate model. One of the first hierarchical models is the AIDA (Attention to an ad message, Interest and Desire for the brand, and Action - buying the brand), developed in the 19th century. This sequence presupposed advertising working entirely in the conscious mind. In the mid 1930's George Gallup developed a measure called "spontaneous recall" which was first introduced as a measure of press advertising effectiveness. Later Claude Robinson developed day-after-recall measure and that was the beginning of a widespread use of recall as a main measure for advertising effectiveness. In order to get more data from an interview, supported recall has been introduced and became very popular, especially in academic writing (Heath, 2005: 4).

Vakratsas and Amber (1999: 30-35) reviewed more than 250 journal articles and books. They found out that studies which consider the effects of advertising fall into one of three categories:

- emotion plays no explicit role,
- emotion plays an exclusive or dominant role,
- emotion as working in conjunction with cognition and experience,
- sequential – hierarchy,
- hierarchy free models (no processing sequence).

Vakratsas and Amber (1999: 32-34) present the evolution of models from relatively simple cognition, where emotion plays no explicit role, to more complex integrative model cognition, affect and experience, where hierarchy is not fixed.

Mehta (1994: 3-11) suggests Advertising Response Modeling (ARM) which integrates two routes of persuasion: systematic or central route (cognitive) and heuristic or peripheral route to persuasion. Hansen (2005: 1435) provides evidence from his research that "emotional activities contribute significantly to the overall effectiveness of communication." However, in his research, he did not find peripheral communication significant. Hall (2001: 15), on the other hand, urges the practitioners in advertising to move away from explicit and implicit reliance on hierarchical models of advertising effects. Hall suggests a

model that places affect and experience at the center of advertising process.

A very promising model is a “hierarchy-of-processing” model from Heath (2004: 30-39), which has been evaluated in several research efforts. Heath provides evidence that shows how advertising can influence brand choice without the need for informational persuasion or high attention.

The basic characteristics of the suggested model summed up from Heath (2007: 30-31) are:

- Attention does not need to be “focused on the ad”. It requires only inattentive, shallow and automatic processing to be processed.
- The evaluation is automatic and therefore likely to be subconscious.
- The message itself does not need to play any part in emotional processing.
- Brand attitude changes will happen automatically and mostly subconsciously.

There are several reasons for choosing a model that focuses on low attention. First, modern consumers are usually exposed to advertisements in low-attention environment, where the focus of advertisers has to be on engagement rather than attention. Second, low-attention model can be used to detect emotions more precisely. These emotions not only play a vital role in consumer responses to advertising but are also expected to contribute more substantially to the usage of emotional advertising in the future.

Research limitations and consideration

From the reviewed literature, we can identify the major limitations in consumer responses to advertising. Each of these limitations has been given careful consideration in order to minimize their effect on reliability when collecting the data.

Cognitive bias

Academics and practitioners have adopted an empirical quantitative approach to the measurement of emotions relying mainly on self-reports. Typically many items, like recall and cognitive associations (unipolar or bipolar), are used because of the simplicity and the ability to measure how consumers store product information in

memory. Verbal measures, however, do not always provide understanding of consumer responses when advertising is not predominantly verbal in nature (Zambardino and Goodfellow, 2007; Shapiro, MacInnis and Heckler, 1998; Vakratsas and Ambler, 1999). A huge critic Hall (2001: 12-13) showed evidence that with traditional verbal self-report survey “no matter how ingenious we are with projective techniques and semantic scales, cognitive bias is inevitable.”

Zambardino and Goodfellow (2007: 30-34) provide a detailed review of many alternative measurement techniques that aim to overcome the limitations of traditional verbal self-reporting. These non-verbal methods can be divided into autonomic, physiological and non-verbal self-reporting. Autonomic measures are methods for measuring facial (e.g. smiling), vocal, and body movement. Physiological measures monitor the change in the autonomic nervous system that accompanies emotions. Instruments can measure heart activity, skin responses, brain activity, and muscle activity. As these methods are “language independent” they may be used in different cultures but they have major limitations as most cannot measure the impact of multiple or “mixed” emotions and are impractical for many marketing measurement purposes. According to Zambardino, Goodfellow (2007: 32), all these are “nowhere near a replacement for traditional tracking methods in the quest to provide an explanation of how advertising is working.”

Poels and Dewitte (2006: 33) reviewed the methodology on measuring emotion in advertising in the last 20 years. They argue that for the measurement of lower-order emotional reactions to print advertisements, autonomic measures are theoretically the most valid since they are not distorted by cognitive processes. However, in current advertising research, the use of these types of measures has been scarce and we cannot conclude much about their predictive validity. That is the reason why the authors recommend visual self-report measures such as SAM. Moreover, they state that the cognitive bias is lower, compared to verbal self-report, and that emotional reactions measured by means of SAM exhibit direct effects on behavioral measures such as purchase intention.

Research bias

Braun and Zaltman (2006: 61) recognized the important role of research bias in academic research. They claim that because participants are “aware that the researcher is interested in assessing their attitude changes based on the advertising exposure”. Thus, they may overestimate or underestimate the importance of advertising by indicating more or less favorable attitudes. The research bias is especially present in outdoor advertising research. As Osborne and Coleman (2008: 13) state, it is much more difficult to create a realistic outdoor viewing experience in a research lab. To minimize the research bias it is important to design research also in a natural environment without any interference of a researcher or unnatural situation for consumers. We see this as a cross validation study guidelines.

Long term effects of advertising

We define the goal of advertising as the creation of lasting memories. Emotional associations definitely contribute to brand equity. Thus according to Braun and Zaltman (2006: 57), advertising should “have an enduring emotional impact on an audience by facilitating their creation of personally relevant understandings of an advertisement.” Similarly Young suggests (Young, 2009: 42) that if an ad “does not leave some kind of lasting trace behind in the long-term memory of a consumer, it is difficult to argue that it had any kind of effect.” In addition, Hall (2004: 4) points out that the limitations of the majority of copy-testing measures are that they tend to “focus on the least-important part of advertising—short-term sales effects.”

To measure long term-effects of attitude change, many authors used techniques of recall a week or more after exposure. They also argue that attitude/belief changes cannot be monitored after one viewing session, and the pre/post designs are often administered over a longer period of time in which consumers have been potentially exposed to the advertising campaign numerous times. Research in cognitive psychology, however, finds that such a delay is not necessary for adoption of information in memory. This is supported by Braun and Zaltman (2006: 57) who tested whether time was indeed necessary for attitude and memory change to occur. They provide evidence that such a delay is not necessary for adoption of information in memory. Their research shows a memory shift in less than 20 minutes. They imply that researchers, when testing the change in beliefs and memory change, can do that in a single

session. According to Braun and Zaltman (2006: 61), the problem of prolonging the time between the exposure and the test is that “in allowing greater time between initial and post attitude measures, more potentially intervening material can also be presented that can interfere with attitudes.” Authors provide evidence that there is a lot less control over the situation in the typical pre/post design compared to a more controlled single session setting.

Discussion and conclusion

A planned research design must be optimized to minimize the mentioned research limitations we have come across when reviewing literature. In addition, a carefully planned sampling and the execution of separate research studies in an environment, which is as realistic as possible, is essential for this research. The future research must be more concerned with the development of new theoretical frameworks with complementary research methods and realistic studies.

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